

Improved Findability of Energy Research Software by Introducing a Metadata-based Registry

Abstract for the 1. NFDI4Energy Conference 2024

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Abstract:

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1 Introduction and Motivation

Energy research software (ERS, as defined in [1]) is required for multiple purposes like visualization of processes and values, e.g., power quality [2], (co-)simulation of smart grids [3], or analysis of transition paths [4]. Within an exemplified research cycle, self-designed ERS is often fundamental for producing new research results while also presenting a result of performed research (see Figure 1).

New ERS is often developed without reusing existing ones. Therefore, a lot of time is spent on (re)developing software instead of doing research slowing down the progress in research.

Especially the findability of research software can be increased with useful metadata stored in a registry which enables the reuse of research software, as described in the FAIR criteria for research software [5]–[8]. Software registries only store metadata for software without the source code of the software while software repositories also contain source code [9]. Therefore, good metadata and a registry are a first step for improving the reuse in ERS and also the whole research process in energy research.

For this goal, we would like to present a concept for a metadata-based registry for ERS based on a good metadata scheme which we already proposed in [1]¹. In the following, we give a brief overview on the related work. Afterwards, we describe our concept and, finally, conclude the abstract.

¹For this abstract, we reuse multiple texts and graphics from that submitted but yet not accepted paper.

Figure 2. A metadata-based registry support the exemplified research cycle of energy research with software usage [18]

3 A Metadata-Based Registry for ERS

Our concept for a Metadata-based Registry for ERS and its usage is shown in Figure 2. First in the research cycle, researchers should be able to use the registry to find relevant ERS. The registry should be based on a new developed metadata scheme for ERS and should reuse existing approaches from other domains like bio.tools².

After downloading ERS, researchers will use it, extend it, and/or write additional code for their research. The new or extended software should be published on any existing software repository. Afterwards, researchers should be able to add their software with good metadata to the registry by using the metadata generation tool. The tool should lower the entrance barrier for creating metadata for all researchers in the energy domain. Therefore, the tool consist of two main functionalities: First, the tool should extract as many metadata as possible from software repositories like GitHub and other sources. Different ways of extracting metadata have already described within SoMEF [16], HERMES⁶, and Betty's Research Engine [17]. Second, the tool should allow researchers to curate all extracted metadata and to add additional non-extracted metadata. The tool should encourage the use of controlled value vocabularies and links to other semantic web sources.

Both the metadata generation tool and the registry are based on a new metadata scheme for ERS. This metadata scheme should be usable for all different types of ERS. It consists of elements describing the categories for the metadata, guidelines for creating according metadata, a syntax, and of constraints for the metadata, e.g., ontologies as value vocabularies [19]. The metadata scheme should be developed as an application profile according to the requirements of energy researchers and by reusing as many metadata elements as possible to foster a high interoperability.

⁶<https://project.software-metadata.pub/>, accessed 10.07.2023

4 Conclusion

There already exist a lot of ERS and even more will be needed in the future. ERS is often developed without reusing existing software because relevant ERS is difficult to find. The overall findability of ERS can be improved through register ERS in a registry with good metadata. Therefore, we want to present and discuss our concept of a **metadata-based registry for ERS** to enable this process on the NFDI4Energy conference. This registry is highly relevant in the context of research software management in the energy domain and we would like to discuss it with the NFDI4Energy community.

We currently perform a detailed requirement analysis based on multiple interviews with energy researchers. We would like to show and discuss first results of the analysis on the NFDI4Energy conference as well.

Author contributions

Stephan Ferez contributed in conceptualization, methodology, writing - original draft. Astrid Nieße contributed in conceptualization, methodology, writing - review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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